

METHODOLOGY OF SPEECH THERAPY WORK WITH MOTOR ALALIA

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ANNOTATION

The methodology of speech therapy work with motor alalia on the basis of a violation of language analysis and is covered on the basis of scientific approaches.

Keyword: *speech therapy work with motor alalia - characterized by a violation of phonemic recognition of sounds, optical, differentiation of mixed letters, develop phonemic hearing, affricate and components, correction of articulatory-acoustic*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Методика логопедической работы при моторной алалии на почве нарушения языкового анализа и освещена на основе научных подходов.

Ключевые слова: *логопедической работы при моторной алалии – характеризуется нарушением фонематического распознавания звуков, оптическая, дифференциация смешиваемых букв, развивать фонематический слух, аффрикат и компонентов, коррекции артикуляторно-акустической.*

In the literature, there are various approaches to the sequence, content, number of stages of correctional and pedagogical influence on children with motor alalia. R.E. Levina, L.V. Melekhova, S.N. Shakhovskaya distinguish three stages of work, O.V. True - four. Speech therapy work should be directed to the entire system of the language: expansion, clarification of the dictionary, the formation of phrasal speech, correction of sound pronunciation.

At the first stage of correctional and pedagogical work, tasks are solved to form the psychological prerequisites for speech activity, overcome speech negativism, develop general and speech motor skills, form game activities, correct visual, auditory, tactile perception, develop skills aimed at perception, comprehension and understanding of speech communication .

The teacher-speech therapist carries out work to overcome speech negativism. To do this, the teacher creates game situations, attracts the child to productive joint activities (drawing, modeling, etc.). This work (stimulating the desire to speak), which is the main one at the preparatory stage, is carried out in parallel with the enrichment of the vocabulary.

An important point in the work of a speech therapist teacher is the use of tasks aimed at developing speech understanding. In understanding speech, the child relies not on the different sound expression of words, but on the broad context of the question. Therefore, the questions of a speech therapist teacher in conversations aimed at revealing the understanding of words, sentences, should contain prompting words.

At the preparatory stage, work is underway to develop the predicative function of speech and prevent the appearance of agrammatism by mastering the elements of the grammatical structure of speech for a child with alalia. The work is carried out in stages in the following sequence:

Reliance on a one-word phrase

Formation of sentences from two words on the basis of one-layer sentences.

Formation of sentence models from two main members - subject and predicate

The second stage is aimed at developing children's initial speech skills in situations of dialogical communication. At this stage, work continues on the development of general and speech motor skills, all mental processes. The main direction in the work is the activation of the passive vocabulary and the practical mastery of the simplest forms of word formation, inflection. Work is also underway on the distribution of sentences, their grammatical design, dialogue and descriptive storytelling.

The fourth stage is aimed at the formation of communicative skills and coherent speech skills. From dialogue in interpersonal communication, they gradually move on to monologue speech, based on the child's interest in the environment. When working on the development of coherent speech, a series of folded pictures, symbolic images, and key words are used.

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